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On
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(ICMR 2024)

**“Sustainability, Innovation and
Transdisciplinary Research for Tomorrow’s
Challenges”**

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NAVIGATING THE MODERN MARKETING LANDSCAPE: EMBRACING HYBRID MARKETING AS THE NEW NORMAL FOR COMPREHENSIVE OUTREACH STRATEGIES

Atul Kumar¹ and Amol Gawande²

ABSTRACT

Hybrid marketing is a promotional strategy that includes both traditional and digital marketing. Rather than focusing primarily on online platforms or in-person touchpoints, hybrid marketing combines the two to create a more successful and comprehensive outreach strategy. It combines marketing strategies from both groups. This usually starts with defining the company's target audience and the brand's ultimate goal. With the help of hybrid marketing, companies can take advantage of all promotional channels by creating a middle ground and coming up with advertising strategies that cater to both channels. Brick and mortar stores are businesses that use traditional and digital marketing to run both online and offline businesses. There are a wide variety of marketing communication channels for hybrid marketing including print advertising, digital advertising, social media channels, event promotion, sponsorships, email marketing based on user subscriptions and much more. Depending on the medium you choose, you can tailor different messages to different audiences – for example, older vs. younger clients or women vs. male customers. For example, you can place a print ad in automotive, sports, and gaming publications to promote men's shaving creams. You would sell women's shaving cream in women's periodicals. Direct mail can be used to target older consumers, while social media can be used to attract younger buyers. This article proves the hypothesis that hybrid marketing is the new normal.

KEYWORDS: Hybrid marketing, New Normal, COVID-19, Traditional marketing.

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